

SAVE FOOD FOR BEES.**Rajabov Bahtiyor Musulmonovich**

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Annotation: The homeland of bees is South Asia. It is now distributed from the southern latitudes to the Far North. Bees live mainly as a family. One family consists of one mother (also called "king" in the vernacular), several thousand workers and several hundred male bees. Mother bees have a body length of 20-25 mm, a weight of 200-250 mg, lay eggs from spring to autumn, and so on. The wing covers half of the body, nectar, differs by the load on the pollen collector. The reproductive organs of mother bees are well developed. Lives up to 5 years (mothers of experienced beekeepers renew every two years). It lays 2 to 2.5 thousand eggs a day. Worked bees hatch from hatched eggs at 21 days, and male bees hatch from un hatched eggs at 24 days.

When adequate and quality food is stored, bee colonies successfully overwinter and thrive in the spring. In the northern regions of the MDX, 28-30 kg of food is left per bee family for the winter, in other districts it is 25 kg, and in Central Asia it is 16-18 kg. In the fall, some of the honey is replaced with sugar syrup. the bees have to process the sugar juice, turn it into sugar honey, put it in the beehive and cover it.

When sugar juice is used as food, firstly, sugar is several times cheaper than honey, and secondly, bees fed sugar honey are free from consuming black honey, which is a sweet liquid secreted by aphids as agricultural pests. ladi. bees that consume black honey during the winter suffer from diarrhea and become weak during the winter, and in some cases the bee family that consumes too much black honey is completely destroyed. Therefore, while bees are still active during the winter when they are less active, they break down complex sugars into simple sugars that are easily absorbed by the body. They place this simple sugar honey in the place of the larvae that hatch from the last eggs laid by the queen in late autumn from the waxed frames in front of the beehives.

In autumn, when the outside temperature drops, the bees move to the beehive frames in front of the hive where the queen lays her eggs; that is, the heat accumulates in the form of a central herd, and in the first half of the winter it successfully overwinters and thrives in the spring, thanks to the consumption of sugar honey in the mummified frames in front of that nest hole.

In Uzbekistan, mainly bee families are kept in hives, so during the flowering period of quality honey-bearing plants, which are well suited for winter during the main juice collection, half or more than half of the honeycomb frames are separated and tightly closed. nests. In autumn, during the winter collection of the internal volume of the bee family, cotton or honey frames, which are considered unfit for winter, are removed from the family and replaced with frames containing honey from quality flowers stored in special closed nests. It is necessary to pay attention to the presence of pollen in the frames of honey, which are separated.

The food base of bees.

The bees' instincts, conditioned and unconditional reflexes fly out of their hives from early morning to late evening, searching for plants that grow around the apiary and produce flowering sap and pollen, bringing the sweet juice they secrete to their nests. When strong bee families have a lot of succulent plants growing around the beehive, they have time to accumulate a lot of honey in their nests.

There are some areas where bees bring juice during the entire spring and summer season in exchange for the flowering of serasal plants that grow or are specially planted in those areas, and such juices are called continuous juices or successive flowering of flowering plants.

Bees consume large amounts of food for their needs, such as survival, rearing worms, converting plant sap into honey, bee stings, and bees' flight activities. Calculated by A.F. Gubin, the juice-producing plants outside the greenhouse consume honey when they are 1 km away from the apiary.

№	Indicators	The amount of honey
1	to the flight needs of bees	23 kg
2	to the flight needs of bees	25 kg
3	To feed and raise 150,000 worms	17 kg

4	depending on the strength of the bees to overwinter	8-10 kg
5	spring development	20 kg
6	To separate 1 kg of wax	3,5 kg
7	bees to their own needs	90-95 kg

Bees need 23 kg to fly, 25 kg to turn juice into honey, 17 kg to feed 150,000 worms, 8-10 kg depending on the strength of bees for the winter, 20 kg for spring development, 3.5 kg for 1 kg of wax, ie bees consuming 90-95 kg of honey for their needs.

In view of the above, beekeepers from bee families are required to deliver honey products according to the plan. It is necessary to take into account the nutritional value and separation of honey.

Nutrients for rapid family growth.

The juice and pollen brought to the beehives from the field is a factor (ground) for the development of worms in the pollen family. However, if bee colonies do not have flowers that secrete sap during the main juice collection period, they are usually fed sugar syrup mixed with 1 liter of water per 1 kg of sugar once every 3-5 days. Over time, the bees' ability to fly accelerates and the breeding of worms accelerates. Therefore, the family should have enough food (8-10 kg) at this time.

The prepared sugar juice is placed in cellophane bags, the mouth of the bag is sealed with an iron and a needle is inserted in 3 5 places. Bees feed on sap when needed to replenish deficient nutrients. Bread yeast or brewer's yeast, which are easily absorbed by bees and contain protein and vitamins, can also be added to sugar juice. Take 250 grams of freshly baked bread yeast, mix it well in 0.5-1 l of sugar juice, then add it to the boiling sugar juice in a bowl, and as a result of boiling, 5% sugar yeast food is prepared, in which the yeast fungi die. Yeast fungi (bacteria) grow and multiply rapidly when dried bread yeast is extracted 4 times less than wet, ie 60-65 grams, dissolved in half fresh water and kept in a warm place for a day. The prepared yeast liquid is boiled in sugar juice and after cooling it is given to the bees.

Foods made from three parts fat soy flour, one part milk and one part beer or bread yeast. If we say that the worms are 100%, 65% of them are fed with a mixture of bees protein. Such a dough-protein mixture is prepared in the following proportions:

№	Types of feed	The amount of feed
1	honey	22%
2	sugar powder	64%
3	beer or bread yeast	5%
4	florist	5%
5	water	4%
6	acetic acid	0,04%

Honey - 22%, powdered sugar - 64%, brewer's or bread yeast - 5%, pollen - 5%, water - 4% and acetic acid - 0.04%. It is best to give this food in early spring, when the weather is bad and the bees are not pollinating the flowers.

Give bees health food.

It is important to feed bees with healthy food to prevent them from getting sick dough foods cost 1-2.5 million per kilogram. When given to bees in combination with biomycin, tetracycline, streptocide drugs per unit, they are free from putrefaction. The farm veterinarian will tell you how much to add to each of these medications, or the medication will be listed on the annotation sheet.

If bees in the apiary are severely infected with nosomatosis, then 4-8 g of fumagillin is added to 1 kg of feed.

A kilogram of yeast food made from a mixture of honey and powdered sugar given to bee families for health purposes is consumed by strong bee families in 7-10 days, which means that bees are treated for as many days. Water is also important in bee life. They consume water throughout the year, but consume more water in the spring when they are rearing large numbers of worms. The average bee family, which lays 1,200 to 1,600 eggs a day, consumes 40-50 grams of water per day. On hot days when there are no juicers in nature, bees bring up to 200 grams of water to the hive. Most of the water supplied is used to normalize the temperature of the hive. As the plants bloom and the bees begin to bring nectar to their hives, the water supply to the beehives decreases. If strong juices come from nature, the bees will stop bringing water

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to their hives completely, as they will be able to meet their water needs at the expense of the water in the juice.

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